

Reviving Heritage: Advanced Stereotomy and Parametric Modeling at the National Palace of Mafra

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In the 18th century, Portugal embarked on an era of monumental architectural constructions, prominently exemplified by the National Palace of Mafra (NPM), a masterpiece designated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2019. The preservation of this heritage also means to comprehend its properties and novelty in the architectural production. Current understanding of this epoch often struggles with limited archival resources, impeding comprehensive historical analyses. This article introduces a novel approach to the study of stereotomy — the art and science of cutting stone into particular geometric shapes — used during this period. Our research focuses on the vaults of the National Palace of Mafra to demonstrate the potential of advanced documentation and modeling techniques in uncovering the complexities of historical architectural practices, that connect craftsmanship and adjustments with geometrical knowledge coming from the treaties. We employ a combination of laser scanning, photogrammetry, and the examination of architectural principles to compile a base of an inventory of NPM vaults. Further, we utilize Rhino Grasshopper to develop parametric models, which enable us to analyze and reconstruct the structural and aesthetic geometries of vaulted ceilings found in the palaceto generate other types of vaults. This method not only aids in the preservation of architectural heritage but also facilitates the creation of a digital library of parametrically modeled stereotomic elements, that could be used to document Portuguese heritage that came after NPM.